

Cor Triatriatum Complicated by Neonatal Pulmonary Arterial Hypertension. A Rare Case Report

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ABSTRACT

We report the case of a newborn who had acute pulmonary edoema and neonatal respiratory distress secondary to pulmonary arterial hypertension; the underlying diagnosis was cor triatriatum. In the short term, this rare anomaly can be fatal. However, if the diagnosis is made in time, it can be completely treated surgically.

Keywords: Cor Triatriatum; Congenital Heart Disease; Pulmonary Arterial Hypertension; Diagnosis; Echocardiography

INTRODUCTION

The Cor triatriatum sinistrum (atrial heart) is an uncommon congenital cardiac anomaly whose diagnostic delay can be fatal, especially when it appears during the first months of life^[1,2]. We report the clinical case of a newborn in whom an acute pulmonary edema led to the diagnosis.

CASE REPORT

We report the case of a 21-day-old male newborn, born at term and resulting from a normal vaginal delivery. Antenatal ultrasounds were unremarkable. His weight and height at birth were 3100 g and 46 cm respectively. There was no notion of perinatal suffering. The beginning was marked by the appearance of dyspnea with refusal to breast from the 15th day of life. The respiratory and hemodynamic state of the newborn deteriorated rapidly requiring a

consultation in the pediatric emergency of the Oran university hospital center and then a transfer to our pediatric cardiology unit. The initial clinical examination was not very contributory in a newborn who was in a state of heart failure, and whose skin recoloration time was prolonged and the peripheral pulses thready, without heart murmur on auscultation. The chest X-ray showed diffuse bilateral alveolar-interstitial opacities indicating pulmonary hyperflow. There is also cardiomegaly with protrusion of the left middle arch (figure 1). The absence of biological inflammatory syndrome quickly ruled out the diagnosis initially suspected of infectious pneumonia complicated by shock. The NTproBNP level was 17,000 pg/ml. Faced with the rapid deterioration of the hemodynamic state, an echocardiography was performed urgently. The diagnosis of triatrial heart was made when a membrane partitioning the left atrium was revealed (figure 2). The membrane was very stenotic, hampering pulmonary venous return, confirmed by the importance of the intra-auricular gradient (gradient of 35 mmhg) and the severity of the suprasystemic pulmonary arterial hypertension (systolic pulmonary arterial pressures PAPs = 85 mmhg) (figure 3). Echocardiography also found significant dilation of the right cavities (figure 4) and signs of venous stasis (dilation of the inferior vena cava and supra-hepatic veins with congestive hepatomegaly) (figure 5). After stabilization of the hemodynamic state, the diagnosis was confirmed by cardiothoracic angio-CT, then the patient underwent radical surgery at 26 days of life, by performing surgical excision of the membrane. The condition of the newborn evolved favorably and the postoperative course was simple. At 3 months, the infant weighed 4800 g and follow-up echocardiography confirmed healing of the heart disease with complete disappearance of the membrane and normalization of pulmonary arterial pressure.

Figure 1: Frontal chest X-ray showing bilateral alveolar interstitial opacities with pleural effusion indicative of acute pulmonary oedema.

Figure 2: Cor triatriatum sinister: trans-thoracic echocardiography 4-chamber view showing an abnormal septation within the left atrium dividing it into the proximal and distal chambers.

RV : right ventricle, LV : left ventricle, RA : right atrium

Figure 3: Trans-thoracic echocardiography doppler using the tricuspid insufficiency jet objectifying very high pulmonary arterial pressures: PAPs (systolic pulmonary arterial pressures) estimated at 70 + 15 mmhg.

Figure 4: Two-dimensional echocardiography in short-axis views: RV/LV ratio > 0.6 = RV dilation. Eccentricity index = 1.53. Eccentricity index of LV denoted as the ratio of the length of two perpendicular minor-axis diameters, one of which bisected and was perpendicular to the interventricular septum. RV: right ventricle, LV: left ventricle.

Figure 5: Expansion of the IVC and SHV with hepatomegaly reflecting right heart failure. IVC: inferior vena cava, SHV: sus hepatic veins.

DISCUSSION

The left triatrial heart is a very rare heart disease. It was first described by Church in 1868, and the name given by Borst in 1905^[1]. It accounts for 0.1% to 0.4% of all congenital heart disease. It is equally considered in both sexes and no genetic predisposition has been attributed to it in the literature so far^[2]. In this malformation, the auricle is

separated into 2 parts by a fibromuscular membrane (figure 6). The left triatrial heart is also called “cor triatrium sinister”. It results from the non-incorporation of the primitive pulmonary vein into the left atrium^[2]. The pulmonary veins then flow into an accessory chamber (proximal chamber = CP)^[3]. This proximal Chamber is separated by a fibromuscular membrane, pierced with 1 or more orifices of variable size from the rest of the left atrium (distal chamber), which is the real left atrium, always comprising the mitral vestibule and the left auricle. This anatomical arrangement makes it possible to distinguish the triatrial heart from a valvular or supra-valvular mitral stenosis, where the left atrial appendages communicate with the proximal part of the left atrium, and which is almost always found in Shone's syndrome (stepped obstacles of left heart). The genetic cause of triatrial heart is still unknown^[3]. The clinical signs are all the more precocious and severe as the orifice separating the proximal chamber from the distal chamber of the left atrium is narrower. The symptomatology is due to venous and pulmonary arterial hypertension^[4]. The atrial septal defect (ASD), when wide and proximal, allows decompression of the accessory chamber in the right atrium. In our observation, the foramen ovale, being restrictive and distal, could not serve as a safety valve for increased filling pressures. When the intramembrane orifice is large enough, this malformation may be clinically silent and discovered incidentally in adulthood^[5]. The diagnosis is based on complementary examinations. The chest X-ray shows indirect signs of pulmonary edema with a normal or slightly increased cardiothoracic ratio. Doppler echocardiography makes it possible to rule out other relatively more common heart diseases such as severe left heart obstruction or abnormal total blocked pulmonary venous return. The section of the 4 cavities shows a membrane dividing the left atrium (figure 2) and makes it possible to evaluate the systolic PAP by Doppler using the tricuspid insufficiency jet (figure 3)^[6,7]. The treatment is surgical. Percutaneous dilation of the intra-atrial membrane by cardiac catheterization has been performed in adults^[8,9]. But healing is only complete after resection of the membrane. The risk of recurrence is exceptional^[10,11].

Figure 6: Schematic representation of a cor triatrium sinister (triatrial heart).

RV: right ventricle, LV: left ventricle, RA: right atrium, LA : left atrium, PV: pulmonary veins, SVC: superior vena cava, IVC: inferior vena cava, PC: Proximal chamber.

CONCLUSION

Cor triatriatum is a rare congenital heart disease with varied presentations. The neonatal clinical presentation can be severe characterized by congestive heart failure with acute pulmonary edema complicated by severe pulmonary arterial hypertension. Echocardiography sometimes coupled with other multimodal imaging modalities may be necessary to characterize, describe and differentiate it from other cardiac abnormalities. It can be definitively curable by surgery if the diagnosis is made in time.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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